

Co-UDlabs

**Building Collaborative Urban Drainage
research labs communities**

D2.5. Report on smart governance and public access to data

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Background: about the Co-UDlabs Project

Co-UDlabs is an EU-funded project aiming to integrate research and innovation activities in the field of Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks and environmental challenges.

Bringing together 17 unique research facilities, Co-UDlabs offers training and free access to a wide range of high-level scientific instruments, smart monitoring technologies and digital water analysis tools for advancing knowledge and innovation in Urban drainage systems.

Co-UDlabs aims to create an urban drainage large-scale facilities network to provide opportunities for monitoring water quality, UDS performance and smart and open data approaches.

The main objective of the project is to provide a transnational multidisciplinary collaborative research infrastructure that will allow stakeholders, academic researchers, and innovators in the urban drainage water sector to come together, share ideas, co-produce project concepts and then benefit from access to top-class research infrastructures to develop, improve and demonstrate those concepts, thereby building a collaborative European Urban Drainage innovation community.

The initiative will facilitate the uptake of innovation in traditional buried pipe systems and newer green-blue infrastructure, with a focus on increasing the understanding of asset deterioration and improving system resilience.

List of acronyms

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning / Full text
CSO	Combined Sewer Overflow
CSO	Combined Sewer Overflow
IoT	Internet of Things
IWGDM	IWA/IAHR International Working Group on Data and Models
JCUD	Joint Committee on Urban Drainage
JRA	Joint Research Activity
RI	Research Infrastructure
RTC	Real-Time Control of urban drainage systems
TA	Transnational Access
UDS	Urban Drainage System
UWWTD	Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive
WP	Work Package
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant

Executive summary

This document is Deliverable 2.5 of the Co-UDlabs project, funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101008626. It summarizes the work on Smart Governance and open data (Task2.3), that took place among partners of the consortium to investigate the evidence-based management of UDS and smart governance practices. **This deliverable presents the findings of an adapted survey, which was designed to assess the current status and challenges surrounding smart governance and open data in the context of EU member states.**

Smart governance in the context of wastewater management is hindered by the limited availability of performance data on drainage networks and special structures across Europe. While legally defined discharge conditions exist for wastewater treatment plants and operators provide comprehensive annual reports to regulatory authorities, there is a lack of information on the functioning of drainage systems, despite the technical opportunities provided by digitalization. Currently, without widespread self-monitoring regulations, the impact of Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) on water quality is mostly modeled and rarely verified through actual measurements. In this study, we therefore ask wastewater operators and utilities across Europe (mostly in the partner countries) what information is available on the functioning of CSOs and how they deal with measurement data, i.e. only use it to improve operation or also share it with regulatory authorities for compliance assessment.

Building upon an existing Swiss study, the survey was modified to reflect the realities of partner countries, including the UK, France, Spain, the Netherlands, Germany, and Denmark. The survey aimed to identify key areas where open data governance can be enhanced through digital solutions and policy frameworks. We first examine the organizational and political obstacles to more effective operation of CSOs. Secondly, we discuss effective measures or incentives to overcome these barriers. The survey included 48 questions and was rolled out from June 24 – October 24, often with the help of national wastewater associations or interest networks, and reached 503 people, of whom 147 submitted a complete response which could be used for evaluation.

Our results indicate that in the partner countries, a large fraction of utilities are already monitoring the state and performance of their urban drainage systems. Unfortunately, this measurement data is mainly collected for operational optimization and is neither used as a basis for decision-making, e.g. by evaluating, checking and subsequently archiving it, nor is it forwarded to authorities for performance monitoring or shared with the public.

Operators seem to be unsure about the current state of legislation but believe they are fulfilling their duties and complying with regulations, unlike other stakeholders. They support using monitoring data for decision-making but are divided on whether sewer performance data should be made public. While operators are not entirely opposed to sharing data, they doubt whether the public would engage with it meaningfully. They are also concerned about potential misuse or overreaction, where real-time data could lead to hasty or inefficient decisions by authorities.

Limitations arise from un-balanced responses, Switzerland dominates answers. Other answers are disturbed by different reality in the partners countries, e.g. a single response for hundreds of systems, because an association-like organization is managing multiple systems at once. Due to the rollout through interest networks, the results are probably biased towards good measurement practices.

To fully tap into the value of measurement data in urban drainage systems across Europe, a uniform strategy should be developed, focusing on the introduction of performance-based targets for CSO discharge behavior. This approach would prevent the accumulation of unused data of dubious quality and ensure that they are used to

better protect streams during wet weather. Public access to monitoring data should be encouraged, but the primary challenges remain organizational, including limited resources and limited skills of the workforce.

Overall, the survey responses paint a picture of a sector undergoing a transition towards a more data-driven approach to manage urban drainage systems. While significant progress has been made in implementing monitoring technologies, particularly for operational purposes, challenges remain in fully leveraging the potential of this data for compliance, planning, and collaborative governance. Addressing these challenges through targeted policy interventions, capacity building initiatives, and a commitment to data sharing and transparency will be crucial to realize the full benefits of smart governance in urban drainage systems.

1. Introduction: Improvements in water protection require more than just technical solutions

"Implementing CSO monitoring has been a game-changer for us. Before, overflow events could go undetected for weeks or even months, impacting water quality without our knowledge. Now, with real-time monitoring, we detect spills almost immediately and can respond before they escalate. As early detection through simple Event-Duration-Monitoring has made a visible difference in our operations and environmental impact, we are rolling it out to more than 1'500 CSOs in the coming year. Large scale monitoring will not only improve our compliance but has already strengthened our relationship with the community as we actively protect local water bodies. "

— Utility Representative

Smart governance in environmental and wastewater management involves the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to improve decision-making and collaboration among stakeholders (Pereira et al., 2018), specifically "the capacity of employing intelligent and adaptive acts and activities of looking after and making decisions about something" (Scholl and AlAwadhi, 2016). Despite ICT, it emphasizes the citizens' role in collaborative decision-making and collaboration between stakeholders to enhance decision-making, improve public services, and promote transparency and accountability in governance systems (Pereira et al., 2018).

It is a key component of smart cities, aiming to enhance sustainability through technology-enabled citizen participation and open governance (Lopes, 2017; Tomor et al., 2019). In the context of water management, smart governance incorporates cyber-physical systems, such as Digital Twins, for monitoring, management, and governance of hydrological systems (Alexandra et al., 2023). It addresses challenges such as water supply, sanitation, and sustainable water management in urban areas (Sharma et al., 2020). Smart applications using Internet of Things (IoT) techniques are employed for water, waste, air pollution, and transportation management (Salman and Hasar, 2023). However, the implementation of smart governance requires overcoming institutional and organizational barriers (Manny et al., 2021; Marava et al., 2018) and considering social and ecosystem dimensions for sustainable transformations (Alexandra et al., 2023). Another cornerstone of smart governance is engaging citizens through digital platforms, which empowers individuals to actively contribute to the decision-making process and shape policies. By leveraging tools such as online surveys, participatory budgeting platforms, and interactive forums, governments can gather valuable feedback, understand public priorities, and foster a sense of community ownership over initiatives. Citizen participation, transparency and accountability not only strengthen trust in governance but also results in more informed and representative policy outcomes (Sanders, 2019).

In the domain of urban drainage systems, traditional Regulatory Frameworks (Woods-Ballard and Cherrier, 2019) overlooked ICT to improve decision-making and collaboration among stakeholders CSO monitoring, because traditionally, without cell phone technologies, such as wireless data transmission and long-life power supply, it was very costly to monitor underground infrastructure, such as urban drainage systems (Blumensaat et al., 2017). However, recent developments with readily accessible dashboards and open databases, for example in the UK and the USA, suggest that smart governance can significantly enhance the way these systems are designed, managed, and monitored (DEFRA, 2024; Sanders, 2019; Thames Water, 2024).

1.1. The transformative role of smart governance in improving urban drainage management

The integration of smart governance within urban drainage systems is fundamentally anchored in real-time monitoring and data analysis. Sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices deployed across urban drainage infrastructure can provide continuous, granular insights into critical parameters such as water levels, flow rates, and rainfall data. This data collection enables municipalities to monitor conditions that may lead to blockages, or combined sewer overflows, i.e. spills of untreated wastewater at strategic relief points to hydraulically protect the Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP), which are crucial for ensuring the optimal functioning of urban water systems. With these sensors in place, the system can continuously collect data to detect harmful spills early, e.g. during dry weather, recording the real behavior of the systems, which allows for more proactive management rather than reactive responses, especially through the comparison to rainfall-runoff sewer models used for design and assessment.

The analytical capabilities that accompany these systems are pivotal for advancing management strategies. Data analytics and machine learning algorithms can be employed to identify trends in water flow, detect anomalies, and optimize water management. By analyzing this information, authorities can forecast maintenance needs and identify areas requiring upgrades. Advanced models, such as those developed by academic researchers (e.g., (Rieckermann et al., 2017; Schellart et al., 2024)), can further assist in optimizing operational strategies, enabling more efficient urban drainage management across several dimensions:

- **Receiving water protection during wet (and dry) weather:** Despite the potential for improvement, the unmonitored management of stormwater overflows remains a significant challenge for water protection. These overflows can introduce harmful pollutants, particularly when there is an increased intensity in rainfall due to climate change. Stormwater, which often carries debris, chemicals, and pollutants, can directly impact water quality, leading to harmful consequences for ecosystems and human health. Furthermore, as extreme weather events become more frequent, the capacity of many existing urban drainage systems is being tested, pushing systems to their limits. Without comprehensive monitoring, the full extent of these overflows and their impact on water bodies may go undetected, exacerbating environmental damage.
- **Improved Decision Making:** Smart governance tools empower decision-makers by providing them with accurate, timely, and relevant data. For urban planners and water management authorities, data-driven insights help guide decisions about where investments in infrastructure improvements are needed most. By integrating predictive models, city planners can simulate various scenarios, such as the effects of heavy rainfall or long-term climate change impacts, to assess how well drainage systems will perform under different conditions. This foresight enables optimized strategies for stormwater management, ensuring that maintenance activities, resource allocation, and infrastructure development are better aligned with real-world needs. Simulation tools also help predict future challenges and opportunities, which further enhances the agility and responsiveness of urban water management strategies.
- **Enhanced Public Engagement and Transparency:** Smart governance should foster greater transparency, allowing the public to access real-time data regarding the condition and performance of urban drainage systems (Thames Water, 2024). This transparency helps raise awareness about environmental and flood risks, contributing to more informed and engaged communities. In a similar manner, citizen participation

platforms can play a key role in this dynamic by enabling residents to report drainage issues, such as blocked drains or flooding, in real-time. This participatory approach not only allows for a more responsive management of urban drainage but also engages citizens in flood prevention efforts, encouraging collective action. Furthermore, providing the public with access to decision-making processes ensures that there is a shared understanding of stormwater management policies and practices.

- Optimized Resource Management:** In our view, one of the most significant advantages of implementing smart governance is the optimization of resource management. Automation and digital tools allow for real-time adjustments in urban drainage operations, improving the efficiency of resource allocation. For instance, maintenance crews can be directed to areas in need based on up-to-date data, ensuring that interventions are timely and well-targeted (see Section 1). Similarly, Real-Time Control (RTC) can use live monitoring data to maximize the hydraulic capacity, minimize energy consumption and reducing operational costs. This optimization seems especially critical in the face of climate change.
- Climate Resilience and Adaptation:** As climate change continues to alter rainfall patterns and increase the frequency of extreme weather events, smart governance tools play a vital role in ensuring the resilience of urban drainage systems. Predictive analytics and smart models can assist cities in forecasting flooding risks and managing stormwater in advance, reducing the potential for damage and loss of life. These predictive tools enable urban drainage systems to be more adaptable and scalable, adjusting to changing climate conditions with greater flexibility. As cities face rising temperatures, increased precipitation, and changing weather systems, the ability to proactively manage stormwater and protect water quality becomes even more essential.
- Improved Regulatory Compliance:** Last, but not least, urban drainage systems are often subject to traditional regulatory frameworks that aim to ensure the protection of water quality with a planning based approach (Rieckermann et al., 2017). Smart governance tools can streamline compliance with local and EU regulations, helping urban drainage systems adhere to guidelines related to stormwater management and environmental protection. With the use of automated monitoring, reporting, and data collection, WW operators can more efficiently track system performance and ensure compliance with regulatory requirements. Furthermore, by integrating smart technologies into daily operations, authorities can ensure that urban drainage systems are continuously monitored, minimizing the risk of non-compliance due to undetected failures or inefficiencies. This approach also supports broader water protection efforts by extending regulatory compliance and data collection to cover all aspects of urban drainage, as mandated by the European Urban Water Treatment Directive (UWWTD).
- Collaborative Governance:** Successfully implementing smart governance of urban drainage systems relies on collaboration among a variety of stakeholders. Local authorities, urban planners, private stakeholders, and citizens must work together to ensure that data, expertise, and resources are used effectively to address the challenges of urban drainage. This cross-sector partnership is essential for addressing the complexities of water management, which often involves a range of technical, regulatory, and social considerations. Also, this involves making regulatory data accessible to the public, which builds trust and advocates with policymakers and the public.

This clearly shows that there is substantial potential in managing UDS in a smart way. In the future, regulations in the EU consider “adequate monitoring” and using the data in general drainage planning (Table 1). Another key aspect is compliance assessment. This is a fundamental paradigm shift from the traditional planning-based

procedure (developing pollution-control solutions based on pollutant load modelling alone) to a performance-based approach:

“Adequate monitoring is necessary to verify compliance with the new requirements of this Directive concerning micropollutants, non-domestic pollution, energy neutrality, storm water overflows and urban runoff. Monitoring should be supported, where technically feasible and appropriate, through the use of digital tools. In particular for the operational management of collecting systems and urban wastewater treatment plants, the use of digital tools should be systematically considered.”

(European Commission, 2024a)

1.2. CSO Management: Challenges and opportunities regarding the current state of monitoring in Europe

Early CSO regulations prioritized flood prevention and maintaining hydraulic stability at Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) (Schellart, 2024). Design standards relied on simple methods like determining overflow settings based on dry weather flow multiples or runoff estimates from paved areas. While effective at reducing flooding, these approaches often neglected the environmental impacts of untreated CSO discharges on receiving waters.

Modern regulations emphasize pollutant load reductions and receiving water impact assessments, requiring advanced monitoring and modeling. The revision of the UWWTD prescribes to implement UDS monitoring in 2025 (Table 1). However, monitoring, as well as using monitoring data and models for compliance assessment faces significant challenges, including high costs, opaque compliance processes, and ambiguous definitions of permissible or illegal spills.

Shifting focus from increasingly stringent standards to open data initiatives can enhance CSO management. Real-time overflow monitoring and data sharing, providing effective data visualization with context, such as corresponding rainfall data to identify dry weather spills, and public engagement would most probably empower citizens to identify issues and advocate for solutions.

However, today it is not known why exactly there is a lack of measurement data in European countries (JRC, 2019; Quaranta et al., 2022), how the understanding of data handling can be improved among the various stakeholders - so that the real value of the data is better exploited - and which organizational and political instruments would be suitable for improving the enforcement of monitoring laid out in the UWWTD.

Table 1: Implementation planning for the main measures for Urban Drainage Systems (European Commission, 2024a Article 5 and 21)

	2030	2033	2039
Storm water overflows and urban runoff (rain waters)	Monitoring in place	Integrated plans for agglo. > 100.k p.e. + areas at risk identified	Integrated plans in place for agglo. at risk between 10 and 100k p.e.

Therefore, the aim of this analysis is to gain a better understanding of the current status of UDS monitoring, existing or perceived organizational and political obstacles and the possibilities for overcoming them.

Thus, we investigated i) the current status of UDS monitoring in Europe, on the example of CSO equipment and measurements, and ii) the handling of the collected measurement data and the main motivation for monitoring.

To this end, we conducted surveys and interviews and applied descriptive and inferential statistical methods based on a previous study in Switzerland (Manny et al., 2018). They conducted a similar survey and found that, in Switzerland, CSO data is predominantly used for operational purposes (Figure 1). This involves continuous monitoring to adjust system operations, particularly to prevent overflows during dry weather conditions, for example caused by blockage of a pump or flow limiter. Interestingly, the potential for CSO monitoring data was rarely considered (Figure 1, orange and red).

Figure 1: Motivation of wastewater associations (N=90) in Switzerland (Manny et al. 2018) to use measurement technology to monitor CSOs. In order to better exploit the value of the measurement data, they should not only be used for operational optimisation (green), but also as planning bases (yellow) or for success control (red). This survey served as a basis to adapt our study.

In contrast, other European countries increasingly leverage data for compliance with receiving water impact standards (Schellart, 2024; Schellart et al., 2024). For example, England and Wales emphasize data-driven approaches for regulatory adherence and long-term infrastructure planning, showcasing a stark contrast to the limited strategic use of data in Switzerland, where utilities employ monitoring mainly to improve operational aspects. Interestingly, while performance data of CSOs seem to be widely available, and the number of monitored structures seems to be gradually increasing, they are not used for compliance assessment or publicly available (Schellart et al., 2024).

At present, it is not known why data are not shared with third parties (JRC, 2019, Section 2.5.3), and how exactly the understanding of data handling can be improved among the various stakeholders - so that the real value of the data is better exploited - and which organizational and political instruments would be suitable for improving the enforcement of the UWWTD. Thus, the aim of this analysis is to gain a better understanding of the organizational and political obstacles and the possibilities to overcome them.

We have therefore investigated i) the current status of the equipment of CSOs with measurement technology in Europe and ii) the handling of measurement data. From this, we then derived recommendations as to which

instruments in the enforcement or organization of wastewater disposal could help to ensure that the value of measurement data is fully exploited in practice in the future. To this end, we conducted surveys and interviews and applied descriptive and inferential statistical methods based on the results of the Swiss survey (Manny et al., 2018). Simultaneously, the survey aims at engaging the Co-UDlabs community. The responses provide data about the reach of the Co-UDlabs networks and insights to foster participation.

In the following we first present the methodology, then the adaptation of the survey to the individual countries and how we implemented and distributed the survey online. Then we present the results and finally discuss limitations and formulate specific recommendations for science, practice, and regulatory bodies.

2. Methods: Stakeholder survey on organizational and political obstacles regarding smart governance and open data

2.1. Survey Design: structure of the survey and types of questions

In urban drainage, various actors such as operators, authorities, and engineering firms play a vital role in shaping laws, regulations, and practice recommendations, as well as managing wastewater systems. Their actions significantly impact objectives like improving the handling of measurement data.

A previous study conducted a comprehensive analysis of the key actors in Switzerland (Manny et al., 2018), examining their objectives, strategies, and actions, including cooperation and knowledge networks essential for compliance assessment. A critical challenge identified is the lack of knowledge or limited access to key system data, which hampers optimal facility operation, information sharing with regulatory authorities, and overall water protection and planning. Among these stakeholders, wastewater associations were highlighted as key operators of drainage systems. Building on suggestions from (Manny et al., 2018, 2019), a survey was designed for wastewater operators to explore technical, political-organizational, and individual variables. This approach enables the comparison of factors like the number of monitored CSOs or motivations for investing in monitoring equipment across stakeholders in different countries.

The survey employed a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative and qualitative techniques to address five key areas: i) The current state of open data accessibility and usage, ii) Public trust in government and digital platforms, iii) Regulatory challenges and opportunities, iv) Citizen involvement in data-driven governance processes. These areas were structured into 11 groups of questions (Table 2).

1. **General Information:** This section collects basic information about the wastewater association, such as its founding year, the number of employees, the catchment area it serves, and the types of facilities it operates. It also explores the organization's level of autonomy and operational freedoms in relation to the municipalities it serves.
2. **Sewer Infrastructure Elements:** This section focuses on understanding the number and condition of CSOs operated by the wastewater association, including any recent or planned rehabilitation projects. Additionally, it inquires about the number of pumping stations the association manages.
3. **Monitoring Technology for CSOs:** This section examines the specific data points collected by wastewater associations to evaluate the performance and quality of their CSOs. It also explores how this data is managed and shared with external parties. Furthermore, it inquires about the types of monitoring

technologies employed, such as sensors and rain gauges, and identifies challenges faced in deploying and maintaining these systems.

4. **Data Transmission and Management:** This section explores how wastewater associations transmit water level data from their CSOs, with methods including fibre optics, fixed landlines, wireless solutions, and manual retrieval from on-site storage. It also investigates the frequency of data evaluation, the perceived quality of this data, its sharing with external parties, and its integration into wastewater treatment plant process control systems.
5. **Added Value Through the Use of Measurement Technology:** This section seeks to understand the perceived benefits and challenges of using measurement technology in urban drainage systems, particularly for CSOs. Respondents are asked to identify the top three motivators for using such technologies, as well as the top three obstacles they encounter, which may include financial, technical, procedural, or regulatory issues.
6. **Collaboration with Compliance Authorities:** This section evaluates how wastewater associations collaborate with regulatory authorities responsible for urban drainage. It specifically investigates the existence and implementation of integrated drainage plans, offering insight into compliance and collaborative planning efforts.

Table 2: Overview of the survey groups, the number of questions in each group (N) and the description.

No	Group	Name	N	Description
1	3815	General info	9	Basic organizational details, including founding year, employees, catchment area, facilities, and their autonomy in operations.
2	3816	Sewer infrastructure elements	4	Number and rehabilitation status of CSOs, along with the number of pumping stations operated.
3	3817	Monitoring technology for CSOs	3	Data collection practices for CSOs, including monitoring technologies like sensors and challenges in their use.
4	3818	CSO data transmission and management	7	Methods for transmitting CSO data, data evaluation frequency, data sharing, and integration into treatment plant systems.
5	3821	Added value through the use of measurement technology	5	Benefits and challenges of measurement technologies, focusing on key motivators and obstacles.
6	3822	Collaboration with compliance authority	4	Collaboration with regulatory authorities and the status of integrated drainage plans.
7	3823	Further education/ Professional competence	1	Employee professional development activities, such as participation in industry events.
8	3824	Personal attitude of management	4	Management's perspective on outsourcing tasks and future urban drainage strategies.
9	3825	Legal framework and guidelines	6	Regulatory framework for CSOs, covering laws, standards, and performance monitoring.
10	3826	Future improvements	3	Strategies to improve CSO monitoring, including standards, targets, subsidies, and training.
11	3827	Interest in Co-UDlabs	2	Interest in joining the Co-UDlabs early adopter group for updates and collaboration opportunities.

7. **Further Education and Professional Competence:** This section focuses on the professional development of wastewater association employees. It asks whether employees have participated in industry events such as trade fairs, conferences, or events hosted by companies involved in measurement technology or automation, highlighting the association's efforts to stay updated with industry advancements.
8. **Personal Attitudes of Management:** This section captures the perspectives of management within wastewater associations, particularly regarding the use of external services. It asks whether the association outsources tasks like maintenance or data evaluation to third parties and explores management's vision for the future of urban drainage management.
9. **Legal Framework and Guidelines:** This section investigates the regulatory environment surrounding CSO monitoring and management, which is currently changing from a planning-based approach to a performance-based approach with the revision of the UWWTD. It examines how the utilities perceive existing laws and their application, regulations, technical standards, and guidelines specifically related to the performance monitoring and regulation of CSOs.
10. **Future Improvements:** This section identifies potential strategies to enhance CSO monitoring practices. Respondents are asked to prioritize measures such as developing standards for measurement technology, setting environmental targets, providing subsidies, and improving training opportunities. They are also encouraged to propose additional strategies for promoting CSO monitoring.
11. **Interest in Co-UDlabs:** Finally, we were eliciting for the willingness of wastewater associations to participate in the Co-UDlabs early adopter group, which was initially planned to boost the dissemination of Co-UDlabs results and networking among utilities. However, the survey was rolled out with considerable delay, so interaction of the group could not fully develop.

The full survey questionnaire can be found on Zenodo according to Appendix A.

2.2. Adapting the survey to the reality in several European countries

In several meetings with the WP2 core group, we adapted the survey to fit different national contexts to ensure relevance and clarity for stakeholders across various countries. Soon, we recognized that wastewater management practices, regulatory frameworks, and organizational structures vary substantially across Europe. The survey design was tailored as good as possible to reflect these differences in terminology, policy focus, and operational priorities. Each partner translated it to its own language (DE, DK, NL, ES, F, UK). Ethic approval was acquired to roll out the survey in the UK (Appendix D: UK).

The adaptation process involved frequent consulting with project partners in the UK, France, Spain, the Netherlands, Germany, and Denmark to ensure that the survey captured country-specific nuances. Focus groups and expert interviews were conducted to better understand local challenges. For example, in Germany, the survey was pre-tested with industry partners to gauge its appropriateness for local wastewater associations, municipalities, and public drainage operators (See Appendix D). This pre-testing process allowed the survey to be fine-tuned based on direct feedback from practitioners, helping to ensure that questions were aligned with the practical realities and challenges specific to the German wastewater sector. Additionally, adjustments were made

to accommodate specific regulations, reporting standards, and organizational responsibilities within Germany's public wastewater systems.

For other countries, similar adaptations were made based on national priorities and operational standards. For instance, the survey language was translated and nuanced to fit the administrative and regulatory language used in the Netherlands, Spain and the UK, enhancing accessibility and relevance for local operators. By customizing content to align with each country's wastewater management practices, we hoped that the survey was able to capture a more accurate and representative range of responses across the European wastewater sector.

Unfortunately, during the adaptation process, it became clear that the Swiss context for wastewater management was not easily transferable to other countries. Previously unrecognized, this difference highlighted that Switzerland's unique regulatory structures, where wastewater disposal is organized by local or regional associations ("Abwasserzweckverband"¹), and operational practices did not align closely with those in other European countries². As a result, some Swiss-specific survey elements were deemed incompatible with other national contexts by several partners.

Despite this discovery, we decided to proceed with the survey rollout, adjusting only where necessary and focusing on capturing a broader range of insights applicable across diverse regulatory and operational environments. Thus, the survey maintained its relevance and consistency while acknowledging that the Swiss model might present certain limitations in comparability. Also, with the budgeted resources, no further adjustment was possible.

2.3. Data collection process and survey distribution

Data was primarily collected through an online survey, which provided an efficient way to reach a large and diverse group of participants. However, some utility managers who faced challenges in interpreting the questions due to differences in their operational contexts, approached us to perform face-to-face interviews. These interviews were facilitated via Zoom, over the phone, or even in person during business visits to ensure clarity and to accommodate their specific needs. This also demonstrated that the survey was not sufficiently adjusted to the realities in each country.

Based on the good experiences with the previous survey (Manny et al., 2018), we decided to roll out the survey via national and international interest groups or associations, e.g. EWA, GRAIE, EurEau, etc. who would notify their members (data protection: we do not want to collect personal information). The WP2 core group decided that GRAIE was officially mentioned as contact for the survey.

¹ An "Abwasserzweckverband" is a type of wastewater association or utility cooperative commonly found in German-speaking countries, particularly in Germany, Austria, and Switzerland. These associations are formed by multiple municipalities or local authorities who join forces to manage and operate shared wastewater infrastructure. By pooling resources, they can efficiently handle tasks such as wastewater collection, treatment, and disposal.

² In France, wastewater services are generally managed through intercommunal syndicates or delegated to private companies under the "syndicat" model. In the UK, wastewater management is almost entirely handled by regional Water and Sewerage Companies (WASCs), which are privately owned yet highly regulated entities. In Flanders (Belgium), wastewater management is led by Aquafin, a public company established by the Flemish government. Aquafin builds, operates, and maintains major sewer infrastructure and treatment plants, ensuring compliance with European and Flemish standards. Municipalities manage local sewage networks, often partnering with Aquafin for support and expertise. In Spain, wastewater services are competence of individual associations of municipalities which manage urban drainage systems with public companies or by delegation to private companies. In small systems, it is common that public administrations take care of WWTP meanwhile the sewer network is operated by the municipalities or delegated private companies (Schellart 2024).

The survey was first launched at the on June 10 2024 at the International Conference of Urban Drainage (ICUD) conference in Delft, where Wendy Francken (Managing Director of VLARIO, Belgium; Current president of EWA, Former chairwoman of EWA European Policy Committee) was contacted by Eawag and UoS and agreed to promote the survey with their members. An online meeting was scheduled for Wed 18 Sept 2024 to discuss intermediate results and further distribution of final results. Recommendation i) to organize reality check with industry professionals from selected utilities, interest to discuss results at annual EWA meeting.

To facilitate access and promote transparency, the Co-UDlabs team published a dedicated webpage titled "Unveiling the Flow: A Co-UDlabs Survey on Monitoring Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs)." (Figure 2). The webpage hosted the survey in multiple languages and included an outline of survey objectives, target audience, and a brief on the importance of monitoring CSOs across Europe.

Following the announcement in the Co-UDlabs newsletter on June 18, 2024, which introduced the survey alongside other project updates, the link to the survey was distributed via the online portal LinkedIn.com and Twitter.com. Following this, a coordinated series of steps unfolded to ensure broad reach and participation from relevant stakeholders across different European countries. Further details about the individual partners activities to ensure a high return rate and challenges in the data collection process can be found in Appendix D.

In September 2024 the survey deadline was extended due to low response rates in partner countries outside Switzerland (Figure 3). Partners like the European Water Association (EWA) joined in promoting the survey with an email sent out to their members on September 10. EWA committed to circulating the survey link among its members and sent a follow-up email on September 23. Personal contacts in Germany first agreed to promote the survey through DWA in Baden-Württemberg, but later declined the distribution because they feared that it would interfere with a survey of their own.

In October 2024 the survey deadline was extended a second time and finally closed on 31.10.2024.

Figure 2. The survey was published on the CoUDlabs homepage on June 10 2024.

Figure 3. The survey was distributed through email, professional networks, e.g. Komnet (IKT) and social media, e.g. LinkedIn and Twitter.

2.4. Response rates in different countries

The reach of the survey was satisfactory because even some countries were responding which are not among the Co-UDlabs partners (Figure 4). Unfortunately, the number of responses, as well as the representativeness differed a lot across countries (Table 3).

Figure 4. Although the responses are widely distributed across Europe, the coverage is only satisfactory for Switzerland (Table 3). Partner countries in Co-UDLabs are: NL, DK, CH, UK, F, ES, DE

Specifically, after preprocessing (Section 2.5), 147 responses from different countries are available for evaluation. As a rough estimate for how much of the country is covered in the survey, we calculated the sum of the total catchment areas given by the responses. This value was divided by the country's total area. We can differentiate the different countries into the following three categories:

- A. Switzerland: The number of survey responses is satisfactory and sum of the total catchment areas in the survey covers a significant part of the country's area.
- B. Belgium and Luxemburg: A single survey response covers a large part of the country, which provides some degree of coverage despite the limited number of replies.
- C. France, Denmark, Spain, and Germany: the response number is small and covers less than 1% of the country's area. This indicates minimal engagement of the wastewater operators, possibly because the survey did not correspond to their reality, although the partners did their best to ensure a good response rate (see Appendix D).

In Switzerland, Belgium, and Luxembourg, where the survey results can be considered more meaningful, as well as in France, the average share of monitored CSOs ranges between 35% and 50% (Table 3). No responses were received from the remaining countries, although website activity indicated some engagement with the survey. In the UK, the survey was not launched, primarily because compliance assessment and open data practices have been well-established there for many years.

Table 3: Summary of Survey Responses by Country, Including Workforce Size, Catchment Area, and National Coverage (estimated), etc. The coverage is only satisfactory for Switzerland, although for Belgium and Luxemburg, a single reply covers a large fraction of the region. In these countries, the share of CSOs that are monitored ranges between 35% and 42%

	CH	BE	LU	FR	DK	ES	DE
Number of answers	127	1	1	9	4	4	1
Average number of employees	12	1200	100	1912	170	936	42
Sum of total catchment areas (km ²) in survey	6622	13500	515	1691	407	542	86
Percentage of country area covered by survey	16.04%	44.22%	19.90%	0.31%	0.95%	0.11%	0.02%
Total number of CSOs in survey	1792	4500	238	838	534	213	3
Share of monitored CSOs	40.29%	35.56%	42.02%	23.63%	55.99%	62.91%	100.00%

However, due to the way the survey responses were collected, the responses are probably biased towards the monitoring of CSOs, i.e. wastewater operators that are not convinced of the value of monitoring probably did not participate in the survey in general. This is also reflected in the share of survey respondents that wanted to participate in the early adopter group (14%) of innovative utilities or be contacted with further information (20%). The small number of samples of countries other than Switzerland needs to be considered in the further evaluation of results.

The low response rate to the survey can likely be attributed to several factors that affected participant engagement and accessibility: Firstly, the survey length (47 questions) or complexity may have discouraged participants from completing it, especially if they found the questions too detailed or time-consuming. Language barriers or technical difficulties with the survey platform could also have created unintentional obstacles. Second, the timing of the survey distribution may have coincided with peak holiday seasons or busy periods for many organizations, reducing the availability of respondents. More details can be found in Appendix D. Finally, without a strong existing relationship or sufficient follow-up with the target organizations, participants may have lacked motivation to engage, as they might not have fully understood the survey's relevance or the direct benefits of their input. Especially for EU, where monitoring of urban drainage systems is only being introduced now (UWTTD revision). This is different in UK or USA (Bertrand-Krajewski et al., 2020).

Nevertheless, even with an unacceptably low return rate in some countries, the analysis of survey responses can still offer valuable insights if approached thoughtfully. As suggested by Fowler (2013), limited responses may still reveal indicative trends or recurring themes, providing a glimpse into shared challenges, priorities, or innovations within the target group. For example, when responses differ regarding suitable legal situation, or whether sufficient CSO monitoring guidelines exist, this might pinpoint systemic issues or areas for improvement that warrant further exploration.

Moreover, responses from key stakeholders or regions of interest can offer targeted and meaningful insights. When data comes from areas with substantial coverage (category B), it can provide valuable context and help shape broader understandings, even if it only comes from a single large wastewater operator. These insights can also serve as a preliminary benchmark for future studies, allowing for comparisons over time and to improve outreach strategies.

2.5. Pre-processing of the responses and data cleaning

To ensure the quality and reliability of the responses, we pre-processed and cleaned the raw survey data in four steps:

1. **IP Addresses:** We added the locations of the respondents' IP addresses to the survey data using the service from ipinfo.io. We then analyzed the origins of the IP addresses to assess the geographical reach of the survey, as shown in Figure 4. The origin country of the response was assigned according to its IP Location.
2. **Data Cleaning on the Response Level:** Only complete responses were retained, as incomplete surveys may suggest insufficient attention during completion. Responses with unusually short completion times (less than 5 minutes) were flagged for quality checking. Responses from the same IP address were cross-checked to identify any duplicate submissions. Additionally, responses from the same wastewater association were reviewed to ensure the data was not repeated.
3. **Consistency Check on the Question Level:** We conducted consistency checks on specific questions where applicable. For example, for questions with limits on the number of selections (such as “Select a maximum of 3”), we verified that respondents adhered to the instructions and selected only the allowed number of options. However, where removing these responses would have reduced the sampling size significantly and where it was reasonable considering the question, we decided to also admit responses with more than 3 answers.

4. **Removal of Sensitive Information:** We removed any sensitive data, including IP addresses and contact information, to ensure privacy. We then securely stored the anonymized dataset for further analysis and evaluation.

To ensure reproducibility, the cleaned, anonymized dataset is available in CSV-format on the Zenodo Co-UDLabs community³, together with the Python-code used for preprocessing and data analysis as well as the output of the data analysis.

2.6. Data analysis

As described above (Section 1.2), the overarching research questions aim to explore the scope of utilities and their current monitoring practices as well as future vision concerning smart governance. This concept encompasses evidence-based CSO management and collaborative governance, with a particular emphasis on transparency. Specifically, we asked five narrow research questions from different dimensions:

1. **Infrastructure and Facilities Management (RQ1):** What is the scope of wastewater infrastructure managed by wastewater operators, do they only manage the sewer system, or also the WWTP?
2. **Monitoring and Technology Implementation (RQ2):** How are wastewater operators integrating measurement technologies into their operations, including data transmission and the monitoring of CSOs, water quality, and spill data, and what are the challenges and opportunities associated with this data collection?
3. **Data Quality, Assessment, and Use (RQ3):** What is the perceived quality of monitoring data collected by wastewater operators, and how do they assess data uncertainty and use the data for performance evaluation and decision-making?
4. **Regulatory Compliance and Legal Framework (RQ4):** How do wastewater operators navigate the regulatory landscape regarding CSO management, including the application and enforcement of technical standards, performance monitoring regulations, and legal obligations?
5. **Future Vision and Collaboration (RQ5):** What are the attitudes and perspectives of wastewater associations towards the future of urban drainage management, particularly in relation to technological innovations, data transparency, and collaboration with regulatory authorities and other stakeholders?

To present the descriptive analysis of our main findings, we visualized selected questions using bar charts. Detailed visualizations for the complete questionnaire can be found in English language in the Appendix A. Due to the logical sequence of the questions, it must be noted that not all questions were answered by all survey respondents, because paths are conditional and dependent on previous questions. Therefore, the sample size (N) is indicated for each of the created plots. In the remainder of this report, the responses from all countries will be evaluated together.

The data was analysed in a Python-code using the Pandas package and visualized using the Altair package. The appendices for the different countries were generated automatically.

To obtain more insights into ‘professional behaviour’ of wastewater operators, we also performed explanatory analysis using a simple logistic regression approach. This allows us to estimate the probability of specific

³ 10.5281/zenodo.14280836

professional behaviour or attitude based on key predictor variables related to characteristics of the respondent's wastewater organization.

As suggested by Manny et al. (2019), we investigated the influence of various independent variables (X) onto the following three dependent variables (Y) from the survey responses, with the name of the variable given in brackets the variable name:

- **Y1 – Data sharing [ORGshare]:** Our organization shares data with regulators for Compliance assessment
- **Y2 – Performance assessment [MEASplants]:** Performance monitoring and performance review is a main reason why our wastewater association decided to use measurement technology on the plants.
- **Y3 – Vision of public monitoring data [CSOpublic]:** I am in favor of the following vision of the future: "In the future, monitoring data from CSOs are made publicly available on a transparent and easily accessible platform that empowers communities and stakeholders with real-time information about sewer systems and their impact on the environment. By openly sharing data on sewer infrastructure, performance, and maintenance, we aim to foster collaboration, innovation, and informed decision-making, ultimately enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of our wastewater management practices."

The five independent variables relate to the characteristics of the wastewater association regarding age, size, management, participation in professional events and treatment of data:

- **X1 – year:** In what year was your organization founded? Here, one of 3 different categories is assigned according to the age of the organization (before 1970, 1970-1980, after 1980).
- **X2 – Nemployees:** How many people does your organization employ today? For the regression, the number of employees is divided into the categories small (less than 4), medium, and large (more than 20),
- **X3 – management:** Is there a managing director in your utility or wastewater association?
- **X4 – EMPEvent:** Have employees of your wastewater association participated in a professional event / conference within the past year?
- **X5 – MEunc:** Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data? (Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement, information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc)

The analysis was performed using the Scikit-learn Python package. The data was loaded and cleaned by removing invalid year entries, categorizing the year and the number of employees into predefined groups, and replacing certain string values with categorical labels. If only one of the 5 independent variables in a response was missing, it was imputed with the most frequent value (mode) of each column. One-hot encoding was applied to the categorical features. None of the dependent variables were imputed but only responses with available values were kept. For each dependent variable, K-fold cross-validation (5 folds) was used to evaluate the logistic regression model, with the accuracy and coefficients being tracked for each fold. The average accuracy and coefficients were recorded as results.

3. Results: Monitoring data exists but remains underutilized; governance misalignment persists

Given the low response rate for most countries, the results of the online survey do not provide a representative view of the current practices in Europe. The survey explored different facets of wastewater management.

3.1. Operation of sewer infrastructure elements and technology for CSOs monitoring and data transmission

Survey respondents who operate CSOs
N = 147

What facilities does your utility or wastewater association operate?
N = 147

Survey respondents who operate CSOs
N = 147

What facilities does your utility or wastewater association operate?
N = 147

Figure 5. Operation of CSOs and other sewer infrastructure

Asking the survey participants which facilities they operate, 84.3 percent respond that they operate CSOs. However, in a second question, they were asked after the number of CSOs they operated. This resulted in 11 inconsistent replies. When the lacking answers in both questions are imputed with each other, a value of 90.5% is found for the share of survey respondents which operate CSOs (Figure 5, left).

A reasonable combination of the two survey questions leads to the conclusion that of 80.9% of the wastewater associations who operate CSOs also survey the functioning with sensors of at least one of them. Specifically, Figure 6, right, highlights that the most commonly measured parameter is the water level in the CSO (80.3%), indicating a strong focus on assessing the operational status of the infrastructure and detecting overflow risks.

Share of CSO operators with measurement technology
N = 131

Measured variables and derived quantities in CSOs
N = 127

Figure 6. State of monitoring technology and registered quantities in CSOs

Close behind, spill duration is monitored by 69.3% of respondents, reflecting its critical role in understanding the environmental impacts of CSO events, particularly in terms of pollutant discharge into receiving waters. Additionally, carry-on flows to wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are monitored by 59.8% of respondents, showing an emphasis on understanding the reliability of the entire wastewater system. On the other hand, overflow volume is monitored by only 38.6% of respondents, which could mean that practice is aware that deriving volume from level data just using standard hydraulic formulas is challenging (Fach et al., 2009; LfU, 2012).

Regarding data transmission, the responses indicate a growing trend towards integrating real-time data into centralized systems for enhanced monitoring and operational decision-making (Figure 7, left). Half of the operators (49.6%) transmit directly from "most" of their installations and a quarter (25.2%) transmit data from "some" CSO structures. Interestingly, about 15% of respondents indicate that data is transmitted from "none" of their installations, highlighting a notable portion of utilities that lack such digital connectivity. Meanwhile, 10.4% of respondents report that data is transmitted from "all" installations, demonstrating a small but advanced group of utilities with fully integrated systems. These results suggest that while nearly half of the surveyed utilities have achieved a high level of data integration, there remains a significant gap, particularly among those with little or no direct data transmission capabilities. In our opinion, this points to the need for further investment in digital infrastructure to support comprehensive CSO monitoring and management.

From 80.9% of CSO operators that employ measurement technology, around 30% claim to monitor all their CSOs while the other 70% monitor at least one of them. By design, it can be assumed that the larger CSOs of a wastewater association have priority when it comes to the implementation of measurement technology.

Figure 7. State and mode of data transmission in CSOs

Figure 7 right, shows how water level and spill data from CSO measuring devices are transmitted, based on 147 responses. While landline and fibre optics has probably been the traditional way of transmitting data from remote structures to a central SCADA system (34%), the most common method wastewater operators mention is wireless transmission via GSM (62.6%), which highlights the reliance on mobile networks for real-time data acquisition. A smaller share (14.3%) still relies on manual data collection, indicating limited automation in some systems.

3.2. Motivations for monitoring, infrequent performance assessment and collaboration with regulators

We classified the answers regarding the motivation for monitoring technology in Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs) into three main categories: “operation”, “planning”, and “regulation” (and “other considerations”). As expected, operational motivations dominate, with the majority of respondents emphasizing continuous monitoring to detect incidents, ensuring system reliability and timely interventions. Also, many consider mentioned “making the functioning of CSOs visible” as crucial for transparency and operational awareness. Dynamic discharge control, also known as RTC, (44%) and integrated sewer network management (45%) further highlight the focus on optimizing real-time system operations and jointly operating the drainage system and the WWTP.

The importance of monitoring data for future planning and decision-making is recognized by 43% of operators (light green). This reflects a growing awareness of how accurate data can support long-term investments, optimize resource use, and enhance system resilience. Planning in this context heavily relies on rainfall-runoff models, where monitoring data plays a crucial role in validating and ensuring the plausibility of the model results, especially for scenarios regarding flood-protection or the best cost-performance ratio for the implementation of sustainable urban drainage systems.

Performance monitoring and compliance assessment are cited by only a third (32.1%) of respondents, indicating that the use of monitoring data for regulatory purposes remains limited. This low figure suggests that regulators are not actively promoting or incentivizing the integration of monitoring data into compliance frameworks, which is in accordance that “monitoring” of stormwater systems has only been recently included in the UWWTD.

Motivations for use of measurement technology in plants

N = 106

Figure 8. Motivation for the use of measurement technology in WWTPs

Overall, the results shown in Figure 8 are consistent with previous work by Manny et al. (2019), focusing on Switzerland (cf. Figure 1). The earlier study on motivations for using measurement technology in CSOs shows similar patterns: a strong focus on operational benefits like real-time monitoring and system visibility, while using monitoring data for planning and compliance assessment are less considered. Both results suggest a broader trend of underutilizing monitoring data for regulation and long-term planning. The alignment between our survey and the earlier findings from Switzerland suggests that these issues are not isolated but reflect common challenges in the sector.

3.3. Data evaluation frequency and collaboration in sharing CSO Data

Tapping into the value of monitoring data is only possible if the data are analyzed on a regular basis. Interestingly, the two main responses — about a quarter of the operators evaluate data in near real-time and another quarter evaluate data irregularly — highlight contrasting practices in data management for performance assessment (Figure 9, left). The operators with near real-time analysis represent a proactive approach to monitoring, where immediate insights can support operational efficiency, timely responses to blockages, and better overall system reliability. This group demonstrates the potential of using modern technologies to maximize the benefits of monitoring systems, aligning data use with operational needs and long-term goals.

Figure 9. Frequency of data evaluation for performance assessment and sharing of water level data

In contrast, those that evaluate data irregularly suggest a lack of systematic processes, which could result in missed opportunities to address issues in a timely manner. Irregular evaluation likely stems from resource constraints,

insufficient prioritization, or organizational and operational bottlenecks, e.g. a lack of integration of data into routine workflows.

In a similar fashion, data sharing with consultants, regulators or the public is not common practice (Figure 9, right). A notable 45% of organizations do not share their data, indicating that it is often siloed and not used collaboratively. Among those who do share data, 30% share it with urban drainage consultants, reflecting a focus on technical expertise. Sharing data for the construction or validation of simulation models (20%) and with regulators (25%) is less common, which, again, points to an underutilization of monitoring data for compliance and planning.

Together, these responses highlight a disconnect in the effective use and sharing of monitoring data, which undermines the potential for consistent performance optimization. Additionally, the reluctance of many organizations to share water level data, especially with regulators or for broader urban drainage planning, suggests missed opportunities for collaboration and regulatory alignment.

3.4. Legal framework and guidelines

A comprehensive strategy to protecting receiving waters from urban emissions during wet weather requires all three policy components: laws which set the vision, ordinances that establish enforceable rules, and engineering guidelines that suggest best practices and enable effective implementation. Without one of these elements, the framework risks being either too vague, unenforceable, or technically unachievable.

From the answers of wastewater operators who responded to the questions targeting the legal framework, it seems that there is a clear disconnect between legal requirements and practical implementation (Figure 10, top row). While many operators acknowledge the presence of a legal basis for CSO monitoring, the absence of detailed ordinances or enforceable regulations in nearly half of the cases makes it difficult to translate these laws into actionable and consistent practices. Operators also noted that although technical standards and guidelines are widely available, their use is often not sufficiently integrated with legal and regulatory frameworks. On the one hand, this might limit their impact because the activities are not aligned well with regulatory requirements. On the other hand, if it is not clear that CSO monitoring is required by law, it might make it difficult for operators to justify their expenses to their steering board. This is in line with the findings of Manny (2018), who surveyed operators and regional regulators to determine the most effective measures for improving the use of measurement data in CSO monitoring. Both groups surprisingly favoured regulatory instruments from regional or federal authorities, showing a clear preference for measurable objectives set by higher governance levels. This aligns with our findings on laws and ordinances, suggesting a shared belief that stronger, more directive measures are needed for consistent implementation. As shown in Figure 10 (bottom row), when asked whether all stakeholders follow existing regulations, about a third (36.9%) pointed out inconsistent enforcement. This inconsistency suggests that the current regulations are not as effective as possible, because this not only depends on operator compliance but also on coordinated efforts from regulators, authorities, and other actors.

Figure 10. Availability and enforcement of regulations and guidelines

3.5. Wastewater operators' views on real-time monitoring and public data accessibility

To elicit the opinion of wastewater operators on more visionary ideas regarding open governance, we asked the respondents about their opinion on two future scenarios (here: Visions 1 and 2).

Permanent monitoring (Vision 1): “Stormwater systems and sewer networks are equipped with a large number of measuring devices. The measurement signals are transmitted live to a control system via a nationwide wireless network, automatically checked, evaluated, and archived. This permanent monitoring of the systems is made possible by the advancing technological development in the areas of communication, control, and automation technology.”

Transparency and public data (Vision 2): “In the future, monitoring data from CSOs are made publicly available on a transparent and easily accessible platform that empowers communities and stakeholders with real-time information about sewer systems and their impact on the environment. By openly sharing data on sewer infrastructure, performance, and maintenance, we aim to foster collaboration, innovation, and informed decision-making, ultimately enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of our wastewater management practices.”

The results indicate overwhelming support for this vision, with 87.0% of respondents agreeing that real-time monitoring is a valuable and achievable goal (Figure 11, left). This high level of approval reflects the recognition of its potential benefits, including improved operational efficiency, system reliability, and incident response. About 10% conditionally support the vision, likely dependent on factors such as cost, technical feasibility, or organizational

readiness. Only 3 respondents disagreed, suggesting minimal resistance to adopting real-time monitoring technology. In contrast, the responses to making the data public are more divided. Almost half of the respondents support making CSO data publicly accessible (44%) and half oppose this vision (45%), with about 10% conditionally supporting it. The split suggests slightly higher concerns about potential challenges, such as public misinterpretation of data, privacy issues, or the administrative burden of managing public access to data, than the value of the transparency, collaboration, and trust in the operator this vision could foster. A frequently mentioned concern is the risk of misinterpretation of data by the public, either due to lacking system understanding or due to unvalidated data, which can lead to operators being unfairly blamed. To validate and review the data carefully demands expertise and resources which may be lacking.

Figure 11. Attitude of the respondents to visions regarding real-time monitoring and evaluation of CSO data

3.6. Explanatory analysis

In the explanatory analysis, we performed a logistic regression to investigate, what factors are associated with what explains: 1) Data sharing for compliance assessment (“Our organization shares data with regulators for Compliance assessment”), 2) Performance assessment as a main motivation to adopt CSO monitoring (“Performance monitoring and performance review is a main reason why our wastewater association decided to use measurement technology on the plants.” and 3) a Vision of public monitoring data (“monitoring data from CSOs are made publicly available on a transparent and easily accessible platform”).

In general, we find that organizations founded after 1990 show a stronger alignment with modern practices, excelling in data sharing, public transparency, and performance monitoring. However, smaller organizations face consistent challenges across these areas, likely due to resource and capacity constraints. Leadership seems to play a critical role, with the presence of a managing director and participation in professional events positively influencing outcomes. This emphasizes the value of strong leadership and industry engagement. Conversely, a lack of motivation or ability to address data uncertainty negatively impacts all outcomes, which might reflect that fact that in practice it is challenging to obtain high quality monitoring data. In the following, we present the specific results for the individual logistic regression models (Table 4) and describe our findings.

Table 4: Results of the logistic regression to explain conditions for CSO monitoring and data sharing (Smart Governance).
 Blue: positive influence on the outcome, red: negative influence.

	ORGshare	MEASplants	CSOpublic
year_category_1980_to_now	0.46	0.42	0.08
year_category_until_1970	0.32	-0.11	-0.21
Nemployees_category_less_than_4	0.59	-0.3	-0.24
Nemployees_category_more_than_20	0.41	0.98	0.23
management_Yes	0.22	0.58	0.72
EMPevent_Yes	0.84	0.58	0.45
MEunc_Unmotivated	-0.64	-0.95	-0.44
Accuracy	73.66%	69.52%	61.85%
Sample Size	129	72	118

3.6.1. Using data in compliance assessment

The analysis of *ORGshare* highlights supporting and hindering factors influencing the likelihood of wastewater organizations sharing data with regulators for compliance assessment.

- Positive influences:** Organizations founded after 1980 (0.46) are more likely to share data, reflecting the adoption of modern practices and infrastructure in younger institutions. Participation in professional events (0.84) significantly boosts the likelihood of data sharing, likely due to increased exposure to industry best practices and opportunities for networking. Interestingly, small and large organizations are both more likely to share data than the medium ones with 4 to 20 employees. This could be due to small institutions being dependent on external competences.
- Negative influences:** A lack of motivation to address data uncertainty (-0.64) negatively impacts data-sharing practices, highlighting the importance of building confidence in data quality to foster collaboration with regulators.

3.6.2. Performance assessment as a main motivation to adopt CSO monitoring

In the analysis of *MEASplants* we explored factors influencing the likelihood of organizations citing performance monitoring as a key reason for adopting measurement technology.

- Positive influences:** The large size of an organization has most important influence on the motivation use measurement data for performance assessment. Participation in professional events (0.58) positively impacts this motivation, suggesting that industry engagement fosters awareness of the benefits of performance monitoring. Additionally, the presence of a managing director (0.58) enhances the focus on performance monitoring, emphasizing the importance of leadership in driving data-driven practices. Organizations founded after 1980 (0.42) are more likely to prioritize performance monitoring, reflecting a stronger alignment with modern operational practices.
- Negative influences:** A lack of motivation to address data uncertainty (-0.95) significantly hinders the adoption of performance monitoring, highlighting the critical role of confidence in data quality.

3.6.3. Making monitoring data from CSOs publicly available

- Positive Influences:** Organizations with managing directors (0.72) are more supportive of public data accessibility, highlighting the role of leadership in promoting transparency and collaboration. Participation

in professional events (0.45) also positively impacts this support, suggesting that exposure to industry trends and networking encourages openness and engagement with the public.

- **Negative Influences:** Smaller (-0.24) and older (-0.21) organizations are less likely to support public data sharing, possibly due to limited resources or concerns about the risks of transparency. Additionally, a lack of motivation to address data uncertainty (-0.45) significantly reduces support, indicating that confidence in data quality is critical for encouraging public accessibility.

This model achieves the least accuracy of the three models (61.85%). This is consistent with the assumption that the personal opinion of a respondent is not necessarily affected by the characteristics of the wastewater association.

4. Discussion of survey results: Limitations, strengths, and opportunities for improvement

In general, the Co-UDlabs survey provides interesting insights into the current state of smart governance and open data practices in European urban drainage management. Also, the results agree with similar studies (JRC, 2019; Manny et al., 2018) that in most countries the value of monitoring data is under-utilized. However, the quality of the responses is limited by a low response rate in most countries outside of Switzerland, Belgium, and Luxemburg. Nevertheless, we believe that we can still extract value from the responses, especially for future studies.

4.1. Response Rate and Coverage: A Significant Limitation

The survey faced several challenges that impacted its overall effectiveness and the generalizability of its findings. A satisfactory response rate was achieved in Switzerland where the survey was distributed along a network which had already engaged in a similar survey before (Manny et al., 2019). Participation in other partner countries, such as France, Denmark, Spain, and Germany, was very low. In these countries, responses covered less than 1% of the total area, limiting the ability to draw comprehensive conclusions about practices across the European wastewater sector. The distribution method, which relied heavily on interest groups and wastewater associations, introduced a potential sampling bias. This approach likely attracted responses from operators who are already engaged with or supportive of monitoring practices. Operators who are skeptical of monitoring or who face significant challenges in its implementation may have been underrepresented, resulting in an incomplete picture of the sector.

Due to the low response rates and possible bias, the findings cannot be fully generalized to the broader European wastewater industry. The survey may not adequately capture the perspectives or practices of operators who did not participate, particularly those who are less advanced in their monitoring efforts. These limitations highlight the need for future surveys to employ more inclusive outreach strategies to ensure a more representative sample of stakeholders.

4.2. Addressing Limitations: Extracting Value from Available Data

Despite the challenges posed by low response rates and potential biases, the survey results provide valuable insights when interpreted with caution. Even with a limited number of responses, the data reveals indicative trends and recurring themes among participating operators. These insights offer a glimpse into shared challenges, such as discrepancies in the application of legal frameworks or the availability of guidelines. These trends can highlight systemic issues and areas that require targeted interventions for improvement. Responses from key stakeholders or regions with significant coverage, though limited, offer targeted insights that help shape broader

understandings. For instance, input from a large wastewater operator in Belgium provides a valuable perspective on regional practices and challenges, even when the overall number of responses from that area is low. Additionally, the survey establishes a preliminary benchmark for future studies. As response rates improve in subsequent surveys, this initial data allows for comparisons over time, enabling progress tracking and evaluating the impact of interventions. Also, the openly available data make it possible to further explore results from individual countries, possibly including incomplete responses, where Co-UDlabs is lacking the required resources.

4.3. Enhancing the data quality of future surveys

To enhance future surveys, one should use fewer questions and think about better distribution channels. Simplifying the survey by reducing the number of questions and focusing on clear, concise language can make it more accessible to operators with limited time or resources. Sometimes certain terminology was not entirely clear and reducing the questions to the minimum might also help to better adjust the survey to the diverse realities in Europe.

Second, it will be essential to clearly define the target group. Determining whether to address management or operational staff at a wastewater operator ensures that the survey is directed at the most appropriate audience for the desired insights. In scenarios where the questions were at an individual catchment level, in the countries where they manage many sites as a group, they might not have the detailed information to hand, because the survey is being filled out by someone a bit further removed from the operational staff. This might have been a major reason for the inconsistent responses, where the respondent did not have all the required information for all questions. However, the target group will have to be defined in close collaboration with different partner countries, such that their organizational realities of wastewater management can be respected.

Also, the good return in Switzerland suggests that building stronger relationships with target organizations, such as wastewater associations, is another critical step. Clearly explaining the relevance of the survey to activities of the target association, e.g. current or future guidelines, and emphasizing the direct benefits of participation, such as contributing to better policy-making or industry standards in a region or country, could motivate stakeholders to respond. Expanding the range of distribution channels, including direct outreach via conventional mail, or promotion at industry events, can help reach a broader audience.

4.4. Future Directions

Smart governance in urban water management is evolving to incorporate advanced data practices and collaborative frameworks. To accelerate current developments, one should highlight good case studies as examples, harmonizing data, and align with broader EU initiatives.

Regarding good examples of data-based evidence on the performance of an urban drainage system, a collection of good examples would be beneficial. In our view, the case of Flowbru⁴ exemplifies the potential of smart governance through its innovative approach to real-time monitoring and data integration for urban drainage systems. By using advanced sensors and openly accessible data platforms, Flowbru has demonstrated how transparency and responsiveness can enhance operational efficiency and public trust (de Ville and Verbanck, 2017). According to our results, the main motivations to adopt monitoring technology in CSOs are related to the operation of UDS. Such examples serve as valuable benchmarks for other operators looking to adopt similar technologies.

⁴ <https://hydria.be/fr/carte-interactive-des-sites/>

Also, a critical step for advancing smart governance is the harmonization of data through standardized models and ontologies. The Co-UDlabs initiative highlights the need for unified processes that enable seamless data exchange and interpretation across organizations and regions. Developing shared ontologies ensures that diverse datasets—whether from monitoring devices, regulatory reports, or operational logs—can be effectively integrated and analyzed, for example in EU-Data spaces (European Commission, 2024b). Vice-versa, standardized processes can simplify the use of data for performance and compliance assessment as well as infrastructure planning.

5. Key findings, contribution to the goals of Co-UDlabs and recommendations

In this section, we briefly answer the research questions posed in Section 1.

5.1. Key findings of the survey “Unveiling the flows”

RQ1: What is the scope of wastewater infrastructure managed by wastewater operators?

The survey suggests that many responding operators manage not only CSOs, but also other elements of wastewater systems, such as WWTPs and trunk sewers. This indicates a certain level of integration which requires a coordinated monitoring and management strategy. Unfortunately, the survey results may not be fully representative of the entire European wastewater sector due to limitations in response rates and potential biases towards organizations already engaged in monitoring practices.

RQ2: How are wastewater operators integrating measurement technologies into their operations, including the monitoring of CSOs, water quality, and spill data, and what are the challenges and opportunities associated with this data collection?

The responses indicate that a substantial majority of responding wastewater operators monitor the functioning of their CSOs with sensors, primarily focusing on water levels (80.3%) and spill duration (69.3%). However, a substantial part is also surveying the carry-on flows to WWTPs (59.8%), which suggests an integrated system view of the entire wastewater system. The primary motivation for using measurement technologies lies in operational advantages, such as incident detection, improved system visibility, and responsiveness to issues like blockages or overflows. This corresponds to the findings of D6.4 (SPATIAL MONITORING), that many operators are already surveying their urban drainage systems.

Challenges include the underuse of monitoring data for compliance, strategic planning, and regulatory reporting, which does not tap into the full value of the monitoring data. Inconsistent data evaluation practices delay responses, e.g. due to blockages, and hinder performance improvements, possibly often due to resource limitations and lack of systematic workflows.

RQ3: What is the perceived quality of monitoring data collected by wastewater operators, and how do they assess data uncertainty and use the data for performance evaluation and decision-making?

In general, the operators believe that the quality of the data is good. Because of a very low number of responses, the survey provides only very limited information on reasons of bad data quality and how operators assess data uncertainty. However, operators primarily use monitoring data to track operational parameters such as water levels and spill durations, focusing on real-time system monitoring and incident detection. This indicates that the data quality is perceived as adequate for supporting these operational decisions. However, the survey shows that monitoring data is used far less frequently for compliance assessment and long-term planning. This may be due to a disconnect in regulatory requirements rather than a lack of confidence in the data’s accuracy or reliability for

these purposes. To encourage wider use of monitoring data for compliance, planning, and performance evaluation, it is important to address data quality issues and establish methods for assessing uncertainty. Developing protocols for data validation and quality control could help operators identify and correct errors, ultimately improving the reliability of monitoring data and expanding its use in regulatory and strategic decision-making.

RQ4: How do wastewater operators navigate the regulatory landscape regarding CSO management, including the application and enforcement of technical standards, performance monitoring regulations, and legal obligations?

The responses suggest a notable disconnect between legal requirements and the practical implementation of CSO monitoring and management practices. While many operators acknowledge the existence of a legal basis for CSO monitoring, they also perceive a lack of detailed ordinances or enforceable regulations in nearly half of the cases. This makes it difficult to translate broad legal directions into actionable and consistent rules on the ground that apply to every organization in the same manner. Also, without clear regulatory guidance, operators may face difficulties in meeting performance expectations or justifying investments in monitoring technologies to their governing boards. Furthermore, several responses suggest that not all stakeholders follow regulations consistently, indicating that enforcement may be weak or applied unevenly.

RQ5: What are the attitudes and perspectives of wastewater associations towards the future of urban drainage management, particularly in relation to technological innovations, data transparency, and collaboration with regulatory authorities and other stakeholders?

The survey responses reveal a complex picture, highlighting both enthusiasm for innovation and apprehension regarding certain aspects of open governance.

The responses suggest that wastewater operators show strong inclination towards embracing technological innovations. The vast majority of respondents view real-time monitoring of urban drainage systems as a desirable and achievable goal and agree that it is enabled by advancements in ICT technologies. This positive outlook suggests the operators believe that real-time monitoring can boost efficiency, improve reliability, support quick responses, and benefit the environment. However, the survey shows mixed views on data transparency, especially about public access to CSO monitoring data. Many respondents are hesitant, citing concerns about privacy, public misinterpretation, or the effort needed to manage access. This suggests that while some wastewater associations value transparency, others see practical challenges and risks which limit their support for open data. This complements the findings of Deliverable 6.4., which suggest that *“even simple but widespread (open) data can be very beneficial, for example it allows quickly noticing CSO spills occurring during dry weather. However, data should be made open with due care and in collaboration with local citizens’ interest groups, social scientists and governance experts.”*

5.2. Contribution to the goals of Co-UDlabs

The Co-UDLabs project aims to integrate research and innovation activities in Urban Drainage Systems (UDS) to address pressing public health, flood risks, and environmental challenges. The collaboration in joint research and **networking activities** fosters innovation in UDS, focusing on areas such as (smart) **monitoring technologies** and system resilience, which also involves **policy aspects**, also elicited in this survey.

First, the survey results highlight the value of collaborative networks in advancing the understanding of monitoring practices and addressing barriers to data utilization in urban drainage systems. By providing a shared platform for stakeholders to exchange information, the survey contributes to Co-UDlabs’ mission of fostering connections

between operators, regulators, academic researchers, and policymakers. The survey also supports a better understanding of monitoring practices through networking. For example, it identifies commonly monitored parameters, such as water levels and spill duration, revealing trends and priorities across regions. This information provides stakeholders with a unified perspective on the state of monitoring practices, promoting cross-sector discussions about readiness for adopting advanced technologies. The survey also uncovers significant challenges related to data utilization, including the underuse of monitoring data for strategic purposes, inconsistent evaluation practices, and limited data sharing. These findings underscore the need for stronger collaboration among stakeholders to overcome these barriers.

By leveraging the survey as a networking tool, Co-UDlabs not only deepens understanding of monitoring practices but also creates opportunities for stakeholders to work together in advancing data-driven urban drainage management.

Second, the survey's exploration of operators' attitudes toward real-time monitoring and transparency aligns with Co-UDlabs' ambition to leverage innovative technologies around smart monitoring. Insights into the perceived benefits and obstacles provide a roadmap for advancing urban drainage systems' efficiency, sustainability, and resilience, directly contributing to the project's broader goals.

Last, but not least, by uncovering gaps in regulatory frameworks and the practical enforcement of CSO monitoring requirements, the survey highlights areas where policy improvements are needed. This aligns with Co-UDlabs' commitment to guiding policy development for better urban water management practices.

5.3. Recommendations

Even with limited coverage, we believe that the survey findings offer valuable insights into the current state of urban drainage management in Europe and highlight key areas for improvement across different stakeholder groups. Here, we present our recommendations for wastewater operators, academic researchers, and regulatory authorities.

5.3.1. Wastewater Operators should...

- **Embrace real-time monitoring and data-driven decision-making:** The survey demonstrates strong support for real-time monitoring among operators. Actively investing in and implementing advanced monitoring technologies for CSOs and other urban drainage infrastructure is crucial for achieving operational efficiency, enhancing system reliability, and proactively responding to incidents.
- **Enhance data evaluation and analysis practices:** While real-time data collection is becoming increasingly common, data evaluation and analysis practices remain inconsistent. Establish systematic processes for regularly evaluating monitoring data to identify trends, anomalies, and performance issues, enabling data-informed decision-making for both operational and strategic purposes. To fully tap into the value of your monitoring data, discuss employing digital tools, such as data management systems. Consult best practice guidelines, such as the DWA-M 151 guideline, titled "Measurement Data Management Systems (MDMS) in Drainage Systems," which provides comprehensive guidance on the implementation and operation of MDMS within urban drainage networks. Use the data to answer practical questions, e.g. benchmarking your current rainfall-runoff models, or analyzing imbalances in your spill behavior.
- **Discuss internally the pros and cons of data transparency and public engagement:** While concerns about data transparency exist, consider developing strategies for responsibly sharing CSO data with the public.

Providing clear context, addressing privacy concerns, and engaging with communities can foster trust, encourage collaboration, and promote informed decision-making.

5.3.2. Academic researchers should...

- **Improve data quality and address data uncertainty:** Develop methodologies and tools for assessing and addressing uncertainty in CSO monitoring data, e.g. reliably assessing spill volumes from water level measurements or water quality monitors that work in sewers and with raw wastewater. This includes quantifying uncertainties associated with different sensor types, measurement techniques, and data processing methods.
- **Bridge the gap between research and practice:** Facilitate knowledge exchange and technology transfer between researchers and practitioners. Engaging operators in research projects, disseminating research findings through accessible channels, and providing training on the use and interpretation of advanced monitoring and analysis tools can enhance the practical application of research outcomes.
- **Support the development of open data standards and platforms:** Contribute to the development of open data standards and platforms that facilitate data sharing and interoperability between different systems and stakeholders. This includes developing standardized data formats, metadata schemas, and data governance frameworks that promote transparency, accessibility, and responsible data use.

5.3.3. Local and federal regulators should...

- **Develop clear and enforceable regulations for CSO monitoring and management:** Address the disconnect between legal mandates and practical implementation by establishing detailed ordinances and regulations that clearly specify monitoring requirements, performance standards, and enforcement mechanisms. Start with collecting simple metrics for compliance assessment, e.g. days with spills per year or duration of spills and introduce more complexity as knowledge, data quality and organizational processes evolve in the different stakeholders. Provide clear guidance on the application of technical standards and guidelines in the context of regulatory requirements.
- **Foster collaboration and data sharing between stakeholders and organizations:** Establish policies and incentives to encourage data sharing among operators, regulators, consultants, and researchers. Clear data governance frameworks should be developed to address critical issues such as data ownership, access rights, privacy, and security, ensuring responsible and secure data exchange. When governing upgrades, balance improvements between wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) and sewer systems. Rather than focusing mainly on WWTPs, e.g. with costly micropollutant removal, integrate planning between sewers and treatment plants to achieve a unified and efficient approach, where pollution from each system component is more or less comparable. To achieve this, ideally, utilities should manage sewers and WWTPs as interconnected systems, fostering collaboration and communication within teams.
- **Provide funding and support for demonstrators and capacity building:** Allocate resources to support the implementation of advanced monitoring technologies, even for demonstration purpose, data analysis tools, and training programmes for operators. This investment in capacity building is crucial, especially because the data literacy at (small) wastewater operators is typically low.
- **Promote public transparency and engagement:** Encourage operators to share CSO data as part of a shared public resource, treating it as a commons for collective benefit. Support the development of transparent,

accessible platforms that provide real-time information on system performance, such as CSO spills, to empower communities and foster informed dialogue on urban drainage management.

6. Conclusion

The challenges and opportunities surrounding smart governance and open data remain highly relevant, particularly as the implementation of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) continues to drive significant investments in urban drainage infrastructure. With ongoing improvements to wastewater treatment plants, e.g. elimination of micropollutants, the importance of addressing untreated wet weather emissions from urban areas is becoming increasingly evident. To balance investments across the entire system, including WWTPs and sewer networks, a good understanding of flows and spill is necessary, which is currently lacking. Based on the results of our survey to gain a better understanding of the status of UDS monitoring, including existing or perceived organizational and political obstacles and the possibilities for overcoming them, we draw the following conclusions.

The survey method employed in this study was appropriate for exploring these complex issues, with an online format proving effective for reaching a diverse range of stakeholders. However, adapting the survey to national contexts was more challenging than anticipated, highlighting the need for greater involvement of social scientists, increased budget allocations, and enhanced coordination in future efforts. The limited number of responses, particularly outside of Switzerland, further emphasizes the importance of rethinking strategies for engagement in other countries. Future surveys should consider targeted outreach and recommendations from local partners to ensure broader participation.

The results provide valuable insights despite the methodological challenges. Wastewater associations demonstrate significant use of monitoring data for operational purposes, such as real-time system monitoring and incident detection. However, the data is underutilized for long-term planning and regulatory compliance assessments. This gap underscores the need for a more strategic and integrated approach to leveraging monitoring technologies. The responses also highlight key questions regarding infrastructure management, data quality, and regulatory compliance. Wastewater associations manage diverse infrastructure, including catchment areas, treatment facilities, and CSOs, but face challenges in maintaining and upgrading these systems. **While operators claim to comply with regulations, there is skepticism among other stakeholders, particularly regulatory authorities.** This reflects an unclear legal situation that complicates consistent enforcement.

Operators express optimism about the role of digitalization and smart governance in addressing workforce challenges, improving data literacy, and enabling more efficient operations, e.g. with immediate responses during dry weather spills. **However, there is less enthusiasm for transparency and collaborative governance, particularly involving public participation.** This reluctance suggests that while the vision of "doing more with less" resonates, deeper cultural and organizational shifts are needed to embrace open data and stakeholder collaboration fully.

Overall, the responses from wastewater operators across Europe paint a picture of a sector undergoing a transition towards a more data-driven approach to wastewater management. While significant progress has been made in implementing monitoring technologies, particularly for operational purposes, challenges remain in fully leveraging the potential of this data for compliance, planning, and collaborative governance. Addressing these challenges through targeted policy interventions, capacity building initiatives, and a commitment to data sharing and transparency will be crucial for realizing the full benefits of smart governance in urban drainage systems.

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8. Appendices

As the Appendix contains all the details of the survey, it is too long to be included in this file. Instead, it is stored externally in separate files on Zenodo under the following link:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14501655>

8.1. Appendix A - Survey Questionnaire

- A PDF-version of the questionnaire in English is available in the folder “Survey Questionnaire”. In this document, also the logic of the questionnaire is annotated. For each question that does not always appear, the condition based on which it is asked is given.
- A LSS-file of the survey is also available in this folder which contains the complete information about the survey, such as questions and answers in different languages as well as the logic. This file can be imported into the LimeSurvey-server to recreate the survey in the future or use it as a foundation for further inquiries.

8.2. Appendix B - Survey Results

The Survey results are given in different languages for different countries. The responses are filtered respective to the origin of the IP-adress of the respondent. Where only one response was available for the country, the results have the form of a table with the English questionnaire, as well as the language of the Origin country. All results rely on the anonymous data that has been preprocessed. For the others, reports with plots of the answers have been generated for each question. The following files are available in the Folder “Survey Results”:

- **0_clean_anon_survey.csv**: A CSV-file (separator “;”) with the preprocessed, cleaned and anonymous survey results (147 responses). The file is also found in the “Code”-Folder to simplify reproducibility.
- **1_ALL.pdf**: Plots for all survey responses combined
- **2_CH.pdf**: Plots for all survey responses from Switzerland in German language
- **3_BE_table.pdf**: A table for the response from Belgium with questions in English and Dutch
- **4_LU_table.pdf**: A table for the response from Luxembourg with questions in English and French
- **5_FR.pdf**: Plots for all survey responses from France in French language
- **6_ES.pdf**: Plots for all survey responses from Spain in Spanish language
- **7_DK.pdf**: Plots for all survey responses from Denmark in Danish language
- **8_DE_table**: A table for the response from Germany with questions in English and German

8.3. Appendix C – Code for data analysis

In the “Code”-folder, the scripts used for the evaluation can be found to reproduce the results. The following files are relevant:

- *src/preprocess.py*
- *src/generate appendix.py*

- `src/regression_analysis.py`
- `notebooks/deliverable_plots.ipynb`
- `notebooks/countries_overview.ipynb`
- `data/*_questionlist.csv`

8.4. Appendix D – Survey Distribution and Data Collection Process

This Appendix provides detailed information on the distribution of the survey for each country. As described in the main body of D2.5, the survey was distributed across multiple countries through email and online platforms, with tailored approaches for each national context, including collaboration with local wastewater associations to increase credibility. To ensure a high response rate, we implemented strategies such as follow-up emails, offering incentives, and highlighting the survey's relevance to participants' work. We faced challenges like low initial response rates and language barriers, which were addressed by providing translated versions and offering additional support to encourage participation. In the Appendix, the partners answer the following questions:

- **What method(s) were used to distribute the survey?**
- **How was the survey tailored to different national contexts?**
- **What timeline was followed for the survey rollout?**
- **How did you ensure a high response rate?**

Describe strategies to engage respondents, such as involving national wastewater associations for credibility, issuing follow-up emails, offering survey completion incentives, or emphasizing the survey's relevance to participants' work.

- **What challenges were encountered, and how were they addressed?**

Highlight any obstacles faced during distribution, response collection, or engagement, such as low initial response rates, language barriers, or technical issues with the survey platform, and the actions taken to overcome them.